

Welcome to the 4th volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Hello, and welcome to the fourth edition of our Newsletter. In this volume, you will find important updates and conclusions from the EU-HIP Symposium held in Rome, from country-specific needs analyses to progress updates. We will also invite you to attend the CBRN Summit Europe 2025 and introduce you to the BE READY project.

Let's dive in!

EU-HIP Symposium & General Assembly in Rome

We want to thank everyone who has joined us in Rome for the EU-HIP Symposium & General Assembly (Oct 21-23). If you didn't get the chance to participate either in person or online, we have prepared a short recap.

It was a truly productive meeting, featuring presentations from partners across Europe. Denmark, Lithuania, Portugal, Sweden, Germany, and Norway shared valuable findings from their needs analysis; while Belgium, Slovenia, Romania, Iceland, the Netherlands, and Croatia updated us on the progress they are making within this project. We have selected a few examples presented by participating countries that could be interesting for you to read and explore further.

Denmark

The Danish Microbiology Database (MiBa) is a country-wide, automatically updated database of microbiological test results. MiBa was established in 2010 to optimize microbiological diagnostics, infection treatment, control, and prevention by ensuring efficient access to relevant information for healthcare staff, enhancing the surveillance of infectious diseases, and contributing to research and other projects employing MiBa data. Within EU-HIP MiBa will be upgraded to include real-time analysis and improved sample flows. National terminology and value sets that align with SNOMED CT will be integrated into MiBa as well.

Portugal

The Portuguese Directorate-General for Health (DGS) has an information system for reporting cases of mandatory notification surveillance, SINAVE, the National System of Epidemiological Surveillance. Portugal continues to improve the existing system and data collection processes and develops the environmental surveillance module within SINAVE (SINAVEamb) which constitutes an important effort towards the One Health strategy.

Belgium

The Epilabo project consists of a network of sentinel clinical microbiology laboratories coordinated by Sciensano. The system has been operating since 1983 and relies upon the voluntary participation of the laboratories in the weekly submission of diagnostic data for more than 40 pathogens. Building on experience obtained during the COVID-19 pandemic for sustainable Epilabo data collection, Sciensano is moving towards Epilabo 2.0 with enhanced data security, integrity, and quality. Automated data collection and onboarding of labs is expected to start early in 2025.

At the symposium, participating countries reached a consensus on key priorities to enhance interoperability. Some of them include the implementation of FAIR data principles, robust metadata standards, exploring the usage of Electronic Health Records (EHR) for surveillance, development of Common Data Models, integration of standardized terminologies like SNOMED CT and LOINC, using standards for data exchange like FHIR HL7 and strengthening of national communicable diseases registries. A dynamic discussion of applicable AI solutions in Public Health underlined the need for good-quality data to support decision-making.

ATHINA's High Level Architecture

A special thank you to the European Commission, DG HERA representatives for providing a comprehensive update on ATHINA's development. We have been reminded that HERA's mission is to strengthen Europe's ability to prevent, detect, and rapidly respond to cross-border health emergencies. ATHINA will enable HERA to fulfill its mission:

- by providing a secure way of information collection
- by facilitating the analysis, identification, and prioritization of possible health threats
- by facilitating the identification of vulnerabilities in the supply chain of critical Medical Countermeasures

by facilitating the assessment of response options concerning Medical Countermeasures

CBRNe Summit Europe will be heading to Scandinavia for the first time! Taking place in Oslo, Norway where there will be a focus on Arctic Warfare and dealing with CBRNe incidents in freezing conditions. Join us to hear the latest CBRNe capabilities and all the latest threats faced across Europe.

The CBRNe Summit Europe conference, exhibition, and demonstration will take place on the 25th – 27th March 2025 and is supported by the Norwegian Armed Forces. Representatives from EU-HIP will join the Conference on day one within the block Medical Preparedness - Mass Casualty Incidents And Hospital Readiness.

The full [event programme](#) is available and [registrations](#) are open.

BE READY - European Partnership for Pandemic Preparedness

Visit the [BE READY website](#)

In every volume of our Newsletter, we introduce you to ongoing projects around Europe that are worth following. This time we would like to present to you the BE READY project.

The BE READY project aims to lay the preparatory groundwork for the foundation of the future European partnership for pandemic preparedness which includes the preparation of an innovative and visionary SRIA for Pandemic Preparedness as well as the establishment of a secretariat to coordinate the creation of such Partnership between European Commission (EC) and interested partners, with strong involvement of public authorities (policymakers, research funders).

A heartfelt thanks to colleagues from BE READY for their insightful presentation during the EU-HIP Symposium. We encourage you to visit their official website and follow their work!

HAPPY HOLIDAYS
FROM THE EU-HIP TEAM!

We wish you happy Holidays and a great New Year!

Keep following our work. We will enter 2025 with an in-depth overview of Lithuania and more country-specific insights.